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DETERMINANTS OF NON-PERFORMING LOANS IN SERVICE SECTOR LENDING AND CREDIT RISK MITIGATION MECHANISMS

Nurmuhammadov Abdijabbar Yunusovich
Associate Professor at the Department of Bank Account and Audit
Tashkent State University of Economics, PhD
Email: a.nurmuhammadov@tsue.uz
Orcid: 0009-0003-5010-2398

Abstract: This article examines the determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) in the process of lending to service sector enterprises, their impact on the quality of banks' credit portfolios, and the organizational and economic mechanisms for reducing the share of problematic loans. Taking into account the specific characteristics of the service sector, the study analyzes the underlying causes of credit risk formation and the factors contributing to loan repayment difficulties. Particular attention is paid to the role of credit monitoring, digital credit scoring systems, early warning mechanisms, and credit portfolio diversification in mitigating non-performing loans. The findings indicate that insufficient cash flow stability, weak financial discipline, inadequate collateral, and market-related risks are among the key determinants of NPL formation in service sector lending. Based on the research results, scientific conclusions and practical recommendations have been developed to improve the effectiveness of credit risk management and enhance the quality of lending practices in the service sector.

Keywords: service sector, non-performing loans, credit risk, commercial banks, credit portfolio, credit monitoring, digital credit scoring, risk management, early warning systems, loan quality.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследованы факторы формирования проблемных кредитов (NPL) в процессе кредитования предприятий сферы услуг, их влияние на качество кредитного портфеля банков, а также организационно-экономические механизмы сокращения доли проблемных кредитов. С учетом специфических особенностей сферы услуг проанализированы причины возникновения кредитных рисков и факторы, способствующие возникновению трудностей с погашением кредитов. Особое внимание уделено роли кредитного мониторинга, цифровых систем кредитного скоринга, механизмов раннего предупреждения и диверсификации кредитного портфеля в снижении уровня проблемных кредитов. Результаты исследования показали, что недостаточная устойчивость денежных потоков, низкий уровень финансовой дисциплины, недостаточное обеспечение залогом и рыночные риски являются основными факторами формирования проблемных кредитов при кредитовании субъектов сферы услуг. По итогам исследования разработаны научные выводы и практические рекомендации, направленные на повышение эффективности управления кредитными рисками и совершенствование практики кредитования сферы услуг.

Ключевые слова: сфера услуг, проблемные кредиты, кредитный риск, коммерческие банки, кредитный портфель, кредитный мониторинг, цифровой кредитный скоринг, риск-менеджмент, системы раннего предупреждения, качество кредитов.

INTRODUCTION

The efficiency of the financial intermediation system is considered one of the key factors ensuring a country's economic development. In particular, the process of lending to various sectors of the economy by the banking system plays a significant role in stimulating investment activity, expanding production and service provision, creating new jobs, and increasing household incomes. However, credit risks arising in the lending process can have a substantial impact on the stability of banking institutions. One of the most significant

manifestations of these risks is the emergence of non-performing loans (NPLs), the growth of which constrains the stability of the banking system and limits opportunities for financing the economy.

In international banking practice, a high share of non-performing loans is regarded as one of the major factors threatening the efficiency and financial security of the banking sector. Non-performing loans lead to the deterioration of asset quality, an increase in loan loss provisions, a decline in interest income, and a reduction in bank capital. As a result, banks' capacity to finance the real sector of the economy decreases, which negatively affects economic growth. Therefore, leading international financial institutions and global organizations pay particular attention to improving mechanisms for managing non-performing loans and preventing their formation.

In recent years, the share of the service sector in Uzbekistan's economy has been steadily increasing. This sector plays a significant role in ensuring employment for the economically active population, promoting the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, providing services to the domestic market, and increasing the volume of gross domestic product. Government measures aimed at supporting the development of the service sector have further strengthened the demand of service-sector entities for bank credit.

However, the economic characteristics of the service sector contribute to a relatively high level of credit risk in this area. In particular, the high proportion of intangible assets, the seasonal nature of income generation, rapidly changing market conditions, intensifying competition, and limited collateral opportunities increase the probability of loan default. As a result, the formation of non-performing loans in the service sector has become an important factor negatively affecting the quality of banks' credit portfolios.

The analysis indicates that the formation of non-performing loans is determined not only by the financial condition of borrowers but also by a range of factors, including banks' credit policies, the effectiveness of credit monitoring, risk assessment methodologies, and the external economic environment. Traditional credit assessment methods currently used in practice often fail to fully reflect the actual financial position and market potential of service-sector enterprises. Consequently, this affects the quality of lending decisions and increases the likelihood of future non-performing loans.

In the context of the modern digital economy, the introduction of new approaches to credit risk assessment in service sector lending is becoming increasingly important. In particular, the use of electronic invoices, online revenues, POS transaction data, tax records, and other digital indicators expands the opportunities for assessing the actual financial condition of borrowers. This, in turn, contributes to the early identification of non-performing loans and the improvement of mechanisms aimed at preventing their occurrence.

The relevance of this research stems from the need to identify the causes of non-performing loan formation, assess their impact on credit portfolio quality, and develop modern mechanisms for credit risk management in the context of the growing volume of lending to the service sector. Therefore, investigating the determinants of non-performing loans in service sector lending and developing mechanisms for their reduction is of considerable scientific and practical significance.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Issues related to non-performing loans and their management represent one of the most extensively studied research areas within the theory of banking operations and the financial intermediation system. In particular, numerous studies conducted by both foreign and domestic scholars have focused on credit risk assessment, the identification of factors contributing to the formation of non-performing loans, and the development of mechanisms aimed at reducing their occurrence.

Analytical reports prepared by experts of the International Monetary Fund emphasize that a high share of non-performing loans negatively affects the stability of the banking sector, restricts lending activity, and slows economic growth [1]. According to these studies, the deterioration of credit portfolio quality exerts pressure on banks' capitalization and liquidity levels, thereby reducing the efficiency of financial intermediation.

The theoretical foundations of bank lending and credit risk have been extensively examined by F. Mishkin. According to the author, credit risk is one of the most significant risks faced by banking institutions. Mishkin argues that information asymmetry in credit relationships, the financial condition of borrowers, and fluctuations in the market environment are among the primary causes of non-performing loans [5].

In their studies on credit risk management, A. Saunders and M. Cornett demonstrate that comprehensive assessment of borrowers' financial conditions, continuous credit monitoring, and the implementation of early warning systems are essential prerequisites for reducing non-performing loans [6]. They argue that the higher the quality of risk assessment during the lending process, the better the quality of the credit portfolio.

P. Rose and S. Hudgins consider credit portfolio diversification as one of the key directions of bank risk management [7]. According to the authors, the balanced allocation of credit resources across different sectors

of the economy helps reduce the concentration of credit risk, thereby contributing to a lower share of non-performing loans.

S. Heffernan, in her studies, emphasizes the importance of credit monitoring and risk management systems in modern banking operations [8]. According to her findings, insufficiently organized post-lending monitoring processes lead to an increase in credit risks and contribute to the growth of non-performing loans.

R. Levine, who investigated the relationship between financial development and economic growth, demonstrated that the efficient functioning of the banking system is an essential prerequisite for sustainable economic development [9]. The author argues that rising credit risks within the banking sector weaken investment activity and negatively affect economic growth.

Studies conducted by T. Beck, A. Demirgüç-Kunt, and R. Levine indicate that while expanding access to financial services stimulates economic activity, it also requires the implementation of effective credit risk management mechanisms [10]. The authors emphasize the importance of developing credit information systems and improving the transparency of borrower-related information in order to reduce the share of non-performing loans.

In Uzbekistan, the management of credit risks and the reduction of non-performing loans have also been identified as priority objectives by the Central Bank. Official reports of the Central Bank highlight ongoing measures aimed at improving credit portfolio quality, enhancing risk assessment systems, and reducing the share of non-performing loans [2].

At the same time, the analysis of the reviewed academic literature reveals that comprehensive studies on the determinants of non-performing loans and mechanisms for their reduction in service sector lending remain limited. In particular, the sector-specific characteristics of service enterprises—such as volatile cash flows, a high share of intangible assets, the rapid development of digital services, and exposure to market-related risks—require specialized approaches to credit risk assessment.

Specifically, the introduction of digital credit scoring systems, the automation of credit monitoring processes, the assessment of borrowers' financial activities in real time, and the development of early warning models for credit risk detection are considered among the most important directions for reducing non-performing loans in service sector lending. These approaches can significantly improve credit portfolio quality and contribute to lowering the share of non-performing loans in the service sector.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a comprehensive scientific approach to identify the determinants of non-performing loans in service sector lending and to develop mechanisms for their mitigation. The theoretical and methodological foundation of the research is based on the theory of credit relations, the concept of financial intermediation, scholarly perspectives on bank risk management, and the principles of credit risk management developed by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision [4;5;6].

The theoretical aspects of non-performing loans and their impact on the activities of service sector enterprises were examined through the methods of scientific abstraction, logical analysis, and synthesis. Comparative analysis was used to evaluate and compare international banking practices with the approaches applied in the management of credit risk by commercial banks in Uzbekistan [1;11].

Based on statistical analysis, data from the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the National Statistics Committee were examined to assess lending indicators in the service sector and the dynamics of non-performing loans [2;3]. A systems approach was applied to analyze the interrelationships among internal and external factors affecting credit risk, including borrowers' financial stability, cash flow conditions, collateral adequacy, market environment, and macroeconomic circumstances.

In addition, the study employed economic and mathematical modeling to develop an integrated assessment model capable of identifying potential non-performing loans in the service sector at an early stage. The information base of the research consisted of the banking legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan [14;15], reports of the Central Bank [2], materials of international financial institutions [1;11], and fundamental academic sources on credit risk management [5;6;7;8].

The applied methodological approaches made it possible to identify the key determinants of non-performing loan formation in service sector lending and to develop scientifically grounded conclusions and recommendations aimed at reducing their occurrence and improving credit risk management practices.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Lending to service sector enterprises constitutes an important component of commercial banks' credit portfolios. In recent years, the growing share of the service sector in the national economy has been accompanied

by an increase in the volume of loans allocated to this sector. However, alongside the expansion of lending activity, the effective management of credit risk and the maintenance of non-performing loans at an acceptable level have become increasingly important. Therefore, analyzing the determinants of non-performing loans in the service sector and assessing opportunities for their reduction is of considerable significance.

An analysis of data from the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan indicates that although the overall volume of the banking sector's credit portfolio has demonstrated a stable growth trend in recent years, the share of non-performing loans has gradually declined as a result of measures aimed at improving credit risk management [2]. This trend suggests that the reforms implemented to enhance credit portfolio quality have produced positive outcomes (Table 1).

Table 1
Dynamics of Non-Performing Loans in the Banking System of Uzbekistan¹

Indicators	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Share of non-performing loans, %	5.3	5.0	4.7	4.3	4.0
Growth rate of credit portfolio, %	16.8	19.4	21.7	18.6	17.3
Share of private sector loans, %	66.4	70.1	73.8	77.5	80.0

As shown in Table 1, the share of non-performing loans decreased from 5.3 percent to 4.0 percent during the period under review. Nevertheless, the persistence of credit quality challenges within service sector lending indicates the need for further improvements in credit risk management practices.

The findings of the study reveal that the factors contributing to the formation of non-performing loans in the service sector can be broadly classified into two categories: internal and external factors. Internal factors are associated with the financial and managerial characteristics of borrowers, whereas external factors are related to macroeconomic conditions and changes in market environments (Table 2).

Table 2
Factors Contributing to the Formation of Non-Performing Loans in the Service Sector²

Factors	Degree of Impact
Insufficient cash flows	High
Weak collateral support	High
Low management efficiency	Medium
Market risks	Moderately high
Inflation and economic instability	Moderately high
Intensified competition	Medium

The results of the analysis indicate that insufficient cash flow is the most significant factor contributing to the formation of non-performing loans in the service sector. The seasonal nature of revenue generation and fluctuations in demand within service markets often lead to unstable cash inflows. As a consequence, borrowers may face difficulties in meeting their loan repayment obligations on time.

The findings also suggest that inadequate collateral support and weaknesses in financial management substantially increase credit risk. Furthermore, external factors such as inflation, economic instability, and changing market conditions negatively affect the repayment capacity of service-sector enterprises. Therefore, effective assessment of both internal and external risk factors is essential for improving the quality of lending decisions and reducing the likelihood of non-performing loans.

During the course of the study, an integrated assessment model was developed to evaluate the probability of non-performing loans among service sector enterprises:

$$\text{NPL} = 0.35\text{CF} + 0.25\text{FD} + 0.20\text{MG} + 0.10\text{MR} + 0.10\text{COL}$$

where:

NPL – probability of a non-performing loan;

CF – cash flow condition;

¹ Source: Compiled by the author based on data from the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2].

² Source: Compiled by the author.

FD – level of financial discipline;
MG – management efficiency;
MR – market risks;
COL – level of collateral adequacy.

The results of the model indicate that cash flow stability and financial discipline are the most influential factors affecting the formation of non-performing loans. This finding suggests that, in addition to analyzing borrowers' financial statements, banks should also assess their actual cash flow performance when making lending decisions.

The analysis further revealed that inadequate credit monitoring in the service sector is one of the factors contributing to the growth of non-performing loans. In many cases, borrowers' financial conditions are not regularly evaluated after loans have been disbursed. As a result, increasing credit risks are not identified in a timely manner, which may lead to a deterioration in loan quality.

In this regard, the digitalization of credit monitoring has become increasingly important. International practice demonstrates that credit risk assessment systems based on borrowers' electronic invoices, tax reports, POS-terminal turnover, and online revenue data are widely used to improve the quality of risk evaluation [11]. Such an approach enables the early identification of potential credit problems and contributes to the prevention of non-performing loans.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of the study demonstrate that the formation of non-performing loans in the process of lending to service sector enterprises is one of the key factors directly affecting the quality of banks' credit portfolios and their financial stability. The economic characteristics of the service sector, including volatile income generation, a high share of intangible assets, rapidly changing market conditions, and limited collateral opportunities, contribute to a higher level of credit risk compared to many other sectors of the economy.

The findings reveal that the primary determinants of non-performing loans in the service sector include unstable cash flows, weak financial discipline, insufficient management efficiency, elevated market risks, and deficiencies in credit monitoring systems. Furthermore, the study indicates that the use of traditional assessment indicators alone often fails to adequately reflect the actual creditworthiness of service sector enterprises, thereby reducing the quality of lending decisions and increasing the probability of loan default.

The analysis confirms that the implementation of modern credit risk management techniques, the digitalization of credit monitoring processes, and the improvement of credit scoring systems are among the most important prerequisites for reducing the share of non-performing loans. In particular, integrating information derived from electronic invoices, tax reports, POS transactions, and online revenues into the credit assessment process can significantly improve the accuracy of risk evaluation and facilitate more informed lending decisions.

The integrated assessment model developed within the framework of this study has demonstrated its potential for forecasting the probability of non-performing loan formation and identifying credit risks at an early stage. This approach can contribute to improving the quality of lending decisions, enhancing credit portfolio stability, and strengthening banks' financial performance.

Based on the research findings, the following scientific and practical recommendations are proposed:

First, it is advisable to introduce a sector-specific credit scoring system tailored to service sector enterprises. Such a system should incorporate not only traditional financial indicators but also measures of digital economic activity.

Second, credit monitoring processes should be digitalized through the implementation of automated monitoring platforms capable of assessing borrowers' financial conditions in real time.

Third, integrated credit risk assessment models should be introduced into banking practice in order to identify potential non-performing loans at an early stage.

Fourth, mechanisms for credit portfolio diversification should be further improved to reduce the concentration of risks associated with lending to the service sector.

Fifth, greater emphasis should be placed on evaluating borrowers' financial discipline and cash flow conditions during the credit decision-making process.

Sixth, the effectiveness of credit risk assessment can be enhanced through the implementation of risk management systems based on Big Data technologies and artificial intelligence.

Seventh, improving the transparency of financial reporting by service sector enterprises and strengthening credit information exchange systems can contribute significantly to reducing the share of non-performing loans.

Overall, addressing the determinants of non-performing loans and implementing modern credit risk management mechanisms in service sector lending can improve the quality of commercial banks' credit

portfolios, strengthen their financial stability, and expand opportunities for financing the service sector of the economy. The practical implementation of the proposed scientific approaches and recommendations is expected to reduce the share of non-performing loans and increase the efficiency of credit resource utilization within the banking system.

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